

HELP US
LEARN

PHOTO
TRAIL

CHILDREN'S
ACTIVITIES

FREE
FOOD

FREE FAMILY FOOD EVENING

Join us for an evening celebrating
food and its role in local people's
lives.

1st JUNE, 4-7PM

ST GEORGE'S ESTATE

As part of the Food Lives Tower Hamlets programme, Wen and the University of Sussex are hosting an event for St George's residents. Find out about Food Lives, get involved and help us understand how you buy, cook, grow and share food. Tell us what changes you'd like to see, too. You'll get a shopping voucher as a token of thanks for taking part in the research.

WHAT'S ON

OUTDOOR FOOD PHOTO TRAIL

Featuring food photos by Tower Hamlets residents

FREE LOCALLY MADE FOOD

Enjoy delicious dishes from local chefs

FOOD PROJECTS ON THE ESTATE

Find out about our growing spaces, orchard and compost

CHILDREN'S ACTIVITIES

Competitions and activities for children of all ages

TAKE PART IN RESEARCH

Speak to our researchers or take activities home with you

SIGN UP

For future research activities like cook-alongs or interviews

FIND OUT MORE

Email Elaine at e.swan@sussex.ac.uk

Visit <https://tinyurl.com/3dbpj926>

